

Studies on 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles. Part-VII. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Benzalamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide was treated with cyanogenbromide to get 2-amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole which was condensed with different aromatic aldehydes giving the corresponding benzalamino-oxadiazoles. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives have been found to possess a wide range therapeutic activities¹⁻¹¹.

With a view to get better therapeutic activity, we have synthesised 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives of type 3.

Thymol was condensed with chloroacetic acid and esterified with hydrazine hydrate to give the hydrazide (1). 1 was treated with cyanogenbromide and the product (2) was condensed with different aromatic aldehydes to get 2-benzalamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (3). The constitution of the products was supported by ir and nmr spectral data.

The hydrazide (1) gave the characteristic bands at 1660 (C=O str.), 1295 (C-N str.) and 1610 cm^{-1} (N-H def.). The 2-benzalamino-oxadiazole derivatives (3) gave the bands at 1660 (C=N str.) and 1160 cm^{-1} (C-O-C ether linkage str.). The ¹H nmr (DMSO-d₆) for 3 revealed δ 1.1-1.5 (6H, d, (CH₃)₂), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.8-3.5 (1H, m, CH), 4.5 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.6-7.3 (7H, m, ArH) and 3.6 (1H, s, CHAr) [R = *p*-NH₂C₆H₄].

Antimicrobial activity: 2-Benzalamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

(3) were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities by the cup-plate method¹². The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 μg . The compounds were tested against gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus* and gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhosa*. The antifungal testing was carried out with *Neurospora crassa* and *Aspergillus niger*. The physical data are recorded in Table 1. The maximum activity was observed in compounds having R=4-methylphenyl against *S. aureus* and R=cinnamyl against *E. coli*. When R=phenyl and 4-chlorophenyl, the compounds showed good activity against *S. typhosa* as compared to other compounds. Maximum antifungal activity was observed in compounds having R=3-nitrophenyl against *N. crassa*.

Experimental

2-Isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetylhydrazide (1): A mixture of 2-isopropyl-5-methylphenoxyacetate (0.01 M) in methanol (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (80%) (0.01 M) was refluxed on water bath for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from hot water, (76%), m.p. 78°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300, 3200, 1660, 1610, 1295 and 1250 cm^{-1} .

2-Amino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) in methanol (10 ml) and cyanogen bromide (0.01 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 60° for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 155°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3350, 3150, 1660 and 1160 cm^{-1} .

2-Benzalamino-5-(2'-isopropyl-5'-methylphenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 20 ml) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath at 70-80° for 4 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (64%), m.p. 122°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 and 1160 cm^{-1} .

TABLE 1—2-BENZYLAMINO-5-(2'-ISOPROPYL-5'-METHYLPHENOXYMETHYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (3)*

R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Zones of inhibition in mm (24 h)					
			Antibacterial			Antifungal		
			<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. citrus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhosa</i>	<i>N. cressa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
Phenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	122	15	19	15	20	18	15
2-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	163	12	20	16	15	16	20
4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	138	15	19	16	17	17	12
2-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂	150	17	21	19	15	15	16
4-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂	135	17	16	17	20	19	20
4-Methylphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	152	21	20	17	15	18	14
4-Aminophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	150	16	18	15	16	16	17
3-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	125	18	15	16	16	22	18
4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	158	17	21	15	17	16	15
3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	155	19	18	17	14	15	12
4-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	84	16	21	15	16	16	17
2-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	115	16	19	16	15	16	20
3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	111	17	20	15	19	18	14
Cinnamyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	131	15	19	20	15	16	20
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂	159	11	20	15	12	18	12
Chloromycetin	—	—	23	26	21	20	24	23

*All compounds gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis.

Similarly, other substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared. Physical data are recorded in Table I.

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